

1 **Salmonella typhi infection transcriptomics.**

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6 We combined RNA-sequencing with an *in vitro* infection model using human THP-1 monocytic cells to
7 understand *S. typhi* infection dynamics at the whole transcriptome level in an unbiased fashion. *S. typhi*
8 infection resulted in induction of cytokines IL-1b, IL-32 and the cytokine receptor subunit IL3RA. CCL22,
9 CCL5 and CCL19 were activated in THP-1 following *S. typhi* infection, together with CXCL2, CXCL1,
10 CXCR5, and CXCL3. Cells silenced a suite of genes including MGST2, MAN1C1, and SLC16A1 indicating
11 both activating and repressive transcriptional mechanisms in response to or as a result of *S. typhi*
12 infection. Receptor Igsf8 was activated by *S. typhi* infection while Scamp5 was silenced. We present
13 evidence here indicating Sod2 induction is a common transcriptional and cellular feature of bacterial
14 infection in myeloid cells. We present here evidence of a nuclear transcriptional process active during *S.*
15 *typhi* infection in human cells involving ZSWIM4, ZC3H12A, TDRD6, and miR-155. *Salmonella typhi*
16 infection transcriptomics illuminate pathogen-host cell interactions.

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